

An egg intervention improves ponderal but not linear growth among infants 6-12 months of age in rural Bangladesh

Monica M Pasqualino^{1*}, Saijuddin Shaikh², Md Iqbal Hossain³, Md Tanvir Islam², Hasmot Ali², Rezwatul Haque², Kaniz Ayesha², Lee S-F Wu¹, Brian Dyer¹, Khaled Hasan¹, Kelsey Alland¹, Kerry J Schulze¹, Fatema-Tuz Johura³, Munirul Alam³, Keith P West Jr¹, Tahmeed Ahmed³, Alain B Labrique¹, Amanda C Palmer¹

¹Department of International Health, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD, United States of America

²The JiVitA Project, Gaibandha, Bangladesh

³icddr,b, Dhaka, Bangladesh

This work was supported, in whole or in part, by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, Grant Number OPP1163259. Under the grant conditions of the Foundation, a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Generic License has already been assigned to the Author Accepted Manuscript version that might arise from this submission. Researchers at the Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health and icddr,b were responsible for the design of the study. The funder contributed to the design in the study but was not involved in the data collection, analysis, or preparation of the manuscript.

Author disclosures: MMP, SS, MIH, MTI, HA, RH, KA, LS-FW, BD, KH, KA, KJS, F-TJ, MA, KPW, TA, ABL, ACP, no conflicts of interest.

*Address correspondence to MMP. Mailing address: 615 N Wolfe St. Room E2535, Baltimore MD 21205. Telephone: 516-661-0745. Email: mpasqua2@jhmi.edu

Running title: Effect of an egg intervention on infant growth

Clinical Trial Registry: NCT03683667, <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT03683667>

Abbreviations used: ASF, animal source food; GEE, generalized estimating equations; LAZ, length-for-age z-score; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score; WLZ, weight-for-length z-score; WHO, World Health Organization

Word count: 4999

Number of figures: 1

Number of tables: 5

Supplemental Tables 1-4 are available in the Online Supplementary Material.

1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Animal source foods are rich in multiple nutrients. Regular egg consumption may
3 improve infant growth in low- and middle-income countries.

4 **Objective:** To assess the impact of daily egg consumption on linear growth among 6- to 12-
5 month-olds in rural Bangladesh.

6 **Methods:** We conducted a 2x4 factorial cluster-randomized controlled trial allocating clusters
7 (n=566) to treatment for enteric pathogens or placebo, and a daily egg, protein supplement,
8 isocaloric supplement, or control. All arms received nutrition education. Here we compare the
9 effect of the egg intervention versus control on linear growth, a pre-specified aim of the trial.
10 Infants were enrolled at 3 months. We measured length and weight at 6 and 12 months and
11 visited households weekly to distribute eggs and monitor compliance. We used linear regression
12 models to compare 12-month mean length, weight, and z-scores for length-for-age (LAZ),
13 weight-for-length, and weight-for-age (WAZ), and log-binomial or robust Poisson regression to
14 compare prevalence of stunting, wasting, and underweight between arms. We used generalized
15 estimating equations to account for clustering and adjusted models for baseline measures of
16 outcomes.

17 **Results:** We enrolled 3051 infants (n=283 clusters) across arms, with complete 6- and 12-month
18 anthropometry data from 1228 infants (n=142 clusters) in the egg arm and 1109 infants (n=141
19 clusters) in the control. At baseline, 18.5%, 6.0%, and 16.4% were stunted, wasted, and
20 underweight, respectively. The intervention did not have a statistically significant effect on mean
21 LAZ ($\beta = 0.05$, 95% CI: -0.01, 0.10) or stunting prevalence ($\beta = 0.98$, 95% CI: 0.89, 1.13) at 12
22 months. Mean weight ($\beta = 0.07$ kg, 95% CI: 0.02, 0.11) and WAZ ($\beta = 0.06$, 95% CI: 0.02, 0.11)
23 were significantly higher in the egg versus control arms.

24 **Conclusions:** Provision of a daily egg for 6 months to infants in rural Bangladesh improved
25 ponderal but not linear growth.

26 **Keywords:** infants; growth; eggs; animal source foods; Bangladesh

27 **Introduction**

28 Inadequate nutrient intakes and frequent infections contribute to linear growth faltering
29 among infants and young children (1). In Bangladesh, 30.8% of children under five are stunted
30 (length-for-age z-scores (LAZ) <-2 below the WHO growth standard median), a condition
31 associated with increased morbidity and mortality and impaired cognitive development (2-4).
32 Complementary foods in Bangladesh predominantly consist of cereals and tubers that are
33 relatively low in energy and nutrient density; animal source foods (ASF), vegetables, and fruit
34 are typically consumed in small amounts (5, 6). ASF are recognized as important for the diets of
35 infants and young children because they contain high-quality protein, with a full complement of
36 essential amino acids; essential fatty acids, including long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids; and
37 multiple bioavailable micronutrients (7).

38 Although there is evidence that ASF consumption is associated with improved growth,
39 muscle mass, and cognitive function, studies assessing the association between ASF intake and
40 infant and child nutrition outcomes have varied in design and findings (8-13). Trials that have
41 evaluated the effect of ASF consumption on growth have primarily utilized meat or milk and
42 have produced inconsistent results (14-18). Similarly designed trials in Ecuador, Malawi, and
43 South Africa tested the effect of an intervention providing a daily egg over 6 months early in the
44 complementary feeding period. In Ecuador, the intervention resulted in a significant increase in
45 mean LAZ of 0.63 and 47% decrease in the prevalence of stunting in the treatment group
46 compared to the control group, while no intervention effect on linear growth was found in
47 Malawi or South Africa (19-21). Differences in stunting prevalence, background diet, and other
48 contextual factors may explain why findings differed.

49 Eggs are an important contributor to dietary quality. They are a complete protein,
50 containing all nine essential amino acids (22). A cross-sectional study in Malawi found that
51 stunted children had lower serum concentrations of all 9 essential amino acids compared to non-
52 stunted children 12-59 months of age (23). Eggs contain essential fatty acids and multiple
53 micronutrients, including highly bioavailable minerals like zinc, iron, and phosphorus, that are
54 critical for early growth and development (22, 24). Choline is found at a particularly high
55 concentration in eggs. In the egg trial in Ecuador, plasma choline concentration was significantly
56 higher in the intervention arm compared to the control (25). Another cross-sectional analysis in
57 Malawi observed low serum choline to be associated with linear growth failure among 12-59-
58 month-olds (26). Overall, regular egg consumption may be beneficial for growth as they are rich
59 sources of various nutrients (27).

60 As previous trials have produced conflicting findings on the effect of egg consumption on
61 early growth, additional studies in other populations are needed to add other contexts to the
62 evidence base. In rural Bangladesh, we implemented a cluster-randomized controlled trial to test
63 the impact of 3 nutrition interventions (provision of a daily egg, protein-rich blended food, or
64 isocaloric blended food) or control, with or without enteric pathogen control treatment, on linear
65 growth among infants 6 to 12 months of age; all arms received nutrition education. The aim of
66 the present analysis was to evaluate the impact of the egg intervention and nutrition education
67 versus nutrition education alone on linear growth, a pre-specified aim of the trial. By focusing on
68 the effect of an egg intervention in Bangladesh, where eggs are considered an acceptable
69 complementary food, our analysis aimed to be comparable with the egg trials in other
70 populations and strengthen policy relevant evidence for a potentially scalable food-based
71 intervention in a South Asian population (5, 28).

72

73 **Subjects and Methods**

74 *Setting and study population*

75 The study was carried out at the JiVitA Research Site in Gaibandha District located in
76 Rangpur Division in northwestern Bangladesh. The study site was established over 20 years ago;
77 details on the site selection and definition of clusters are reported elsewhere (29). Divided into
78 566 clusters, the site consists of an area of about 430 km². The population of ~630,000 is mostly
79 Muslim. The setting is densely populated and representative of national rural infrastructure,
80 maternal and child nutritional status, and health and nutrition services (29). Numerous cluster-
81 randomized controlled trials and observational studies of maternal and child health have been
82 undertaken at the study site (30-34). A complementary feeding trial (2012 – 2014) reported
83 prevalence estimates of stunting, underweight, and wasting at 6 months as 25.5%, 20.4%, and
84 5.8%, respectively (30).

85 Subjects in the present trial were recruited through an active pregnancy surveillance system
86 in place across the full study area under the mCARE-II trial, which evaluated the impact of an
87 mHealth intervention on antenatal and postnatal care coverage (clinical registration No.
88 NCT02909179). Households were surveyed to identify all women who were married and of
89 reproductive age for enrollment into the pregnancy surveillance system. Women who became
90 pregnant were recruited for mCARE-II. Field staff collected data on women's age and education;
91 husbands' occupation; household size, asset ownership, religion, and access to water and
92 sanitation; and dwelling size and structure at enrollment into mCARE-II. Women were followed
93 throughout pregnancy and pregnancy outcomes were recorded. Infants born to women enrolled
94 in mCARE-II who survived to 3 months of age during a one-year enrollment period (September

95 2018 – September 2019) were eligible for the present trial. Under guidance from ethical review
96 boards, we stopped enrollment after 9 months (July 2019) because accrual of infants into the
97 cohort exceeded projections by ~30%.

98 ***Randomization***

99 The trial had a 2x4 factorial, cluster-randomized controlled design to test the independent
100 and combined effects of a protein intervention and enteric pathogen control intervention on
101 linear growth. The primary outcome was mean LAZ at 12 months. Secondary outcomes included
102 mean weight-for-length z-score (WLZ), mean weight-for-age z-score (WAZ), and prevalence of
103 stunting, wasting, and underweight at 12 months. The first randomly cluster-based allocated
104 factor was masked and was assignment to enteric pathogen control or placebo treatment. The
105 second randomly allocated factor was unmasked and consisted of one of 3 nutrition interventions
106 (i.e., protein-rich blended food, isocaloric blended food, egg) or control. These factors were
107 expanded to 8 groups for randomization. Randomization was blocked by administrative areas of
108 the study site, each containing about 15 clusters, to attain an equal number of clusters and
109 geographic balance across arms. An analyst on the study team conducted randomization
110 sequences using different random number seeds. One randomization sequence was randomly
111 selected among a subset of sequences considered balanced based on measurements of
112 anthropometry and socioeconomic status from previous trials in the study area.

113 ***Sample Size***

114 Based on data from a previous trial (2012 – 2014) evaluating the effect of complementary
115 food supplements on infant growth at the site, an initial one-year enrollment period was
116 anticipated to yield a cohort of 3180 infants (30). This cohort yield would give 80% power to
117 detect a difference in mean LAZ of 0.165 or higher between groups at 12 months based on

118 calculations on mean change in LAZ from 6 to 12 months. Assumptions of $\alpha=0.05$, within-
119 cluster variance in the outcome ($\sigma_0^2 = \sigma_1^2 = 0.3302$), coefficient of variation of the outcome
120 across clusters ($k = 0.2484$), and variation in cluster size from the prior trial to inform a harmonic
121 mean ($m = 5.64$) were applied, as well as a Bonferroni correction for multiple testing (30).
122 However, accrual into the cohort was ~30% greater than anticipated due to an inaccurate
123 assumption informed by pregnancy data last registered at the site (2008 – 2012) that fertility
124 would decline. Based on actual births, enrollment at 3 months, and an estimated 10% loss to
125 follow, we modified the enrollment period from one year to 9 months to yield an anticipated
126 ~5400 outcome measures across all trial arms.

127 ***Intervention***

128 Infants received presumptive treatment with azithromycin (10 mg/kg/d * 3 d) or a placebo
129 administered at ~6 and 9 months of age. The nutrition interventions included provision of a daily
130 protein-rich blended food, isocaloric blended food, or egg for 6 months starting at ~6 months.
131 Nutrition education was provided to all arms. The present study focuses on the egg and control
132 arms, irrespective of the enteric pathogen control intervention. The other arms will be
133 summarized at a later time.

134 Eggs were procured from Kazi Farms Group, the largest commercial producer of eggs in
135 Bangladesh. Kazi Farms Group has an established commercial feed mill that meets European
136 Union production standards necessary to prevent microbial contamination in egg production
137 (35). Field distributors delivered eggs on a weekly basis to households, where they were
138 maintained in study-specific cartons to distinguish them from household eggs. Eight eggs were
139 delivered each week – one egg per day plus an additional egg in case of breakage or spoilage.
140 The first weekly visit was scheduled for the week after the infant's 6-month birthday. If the

141 family was not available, field distributors attempted to visit the household up to 3 additional
142 times or until the infant reached 7 months of age. At the first visit, distributors gave caregivers
143 standard cooking and feeding instructions, including how to clean the cooking and feeding
144 utensils and hands with soap and water. They instructed caregivers to prepare the egg in the way
145 the infant preferred, providing examples that included boiling or frying it, to feed one whole egg
146 each day in addition to regular food and breast milk, to not share the trial eggs with other family
147 members, and to follow feeding guidance from a medical professional if their infant became sick.
148 These instructions were repeated each week.

149 Nutrition education was provided to both arms. Developed based on Alive and Thrive
150 modules, the messages were age-specific and covered topics on infant and young child feeding,
151 including feeding ASF (e.g., fish, egg, liver) daily with dal, fruits, and vegetables; health; and
152 hygiene (36, 37). Messages were standardized and delivered by distributors to caregivers once a
153 month through audio recordings and illustrative pamphlets.

154 *Data collection*

155 Household consent visits, which were scheduled for when infants reached 3 months of age,
156 began in September 2018. In January 2019, 6-month household visits were conducted to collect
157 baseline data on infant characteristics and intervention delivery began. Twelve-month household
158 visits were scheduled through April 2020 but were suspended due to the onset of COVID-19 in
159 March 2020. Interviews were conducted over telephone to reach remaining cases. The data
160 collection period included harvest seasons, Eid-al-Fitr (June 2019), and Eid-ul-Azha (August
161 2019).

162 Field interviewers administered interviews when infants were approximately 6 (baseline),
163 9, and 12 months to the mother or primary caregiver to assess infant characteristics. At each

164 visit, the interviewer asked the respondent if the infant was currently being breastfed. If yes, the
165 respondent was asked how many times in the past 24 hours the infant had been breastfed, with
166 response options including 1-10, 11-20, or ≥ 21 times. Dietary intake was measured at each visit
167 through an infant feeding questionnaire that had been previously evaluated for validity and
168 included a pre-specified list of food and beverage items depending on the infant's age (38). For
169 each item listed, the interviewer asked, "From yesterday morning to today morning, has the
170 infant been fed [the item]?" After completing the listed items, the interviewer asked any
171 additional had been eaten. In the egg arm, respondents were instructed not to report the eggs
172 provided by the intervention because trial egg intake was captured through a separate
173 questionnaire that assessed compliance. Occurrences of morbidity were assessed at the 6-month
174 (baseline) visit by asking if the infant had experienced any signs or symptoms of cough, cold, or
175 difficulty breathing; diarrhea; dysentery; or fever in the last week.

176 Interviewers were trained and standardized in anthropometric measurement techniques and
177 received refresher trainings and re-standardization as needed. Infant length was measured at each
178 visit with a portable length board made locally and standardized against the infant/child
179 Shorrboard (Weigh and Measure, LLC, Olney, MD, USA). Weight was measured using digital
180 infant scales that were calibrated daily by interviewers before household visits (model BD585,
181 Tanita Corporation of America, Arlington Heights, IL, USA). Length was measured in triplicate
182 and the median measurement was used in the analysis. Cutoffs for acceptable inter- and intra-
183 worker technical errors of measurement were set at 1.0% and 1.5%, respectively. As field staff
184 delivering the intervention and those conducting interviews visited households independently, it
185 was possible for the first week of the intervention to begin before the 6-month (baseline)

186 interview was completed. Infants were eligible for the 6- and 12-month interviews until they
187 reached 7 and 13 months of age, respectively.

188 Compliance with the intervention was assessed weekly. At each visit, field distributors
189 asked caregivers to recall, for each day of the previous week, the amount of egg offered to the
190 infant, consumed, left over, or shared. Daily reported consumption was categorized as none, a
191 full serving, greater than half, half, or less than half.

192 *Ethical approval*

193 Protocols were approved by the Institutional Review Boards of the Johns Hopkins
194 Bloomberg School of Public Health (Baltimore, MD) and the Research and Ethics Review
195 Committees of the International Center for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (Dhaka,
196 Bangladesh). Written parental consent was obtained at enrollment into the study. The trial was
197 registered as NCT03683667 at clinicaltrials.gov.

198 *Statistical analysis*

199 Analyses were conducted on an intention-to-treat basis using a complete case approach.
200 Household and parental characteristics data, which were collected through the mCARE-II
201 enrollment visit, and infant characteristics data collected at the 6-month visit (baseline) were
202 summarized as mean \pm SD for continuous variables and number of subjects and percentages for
203 binary and categorical variables by arm. We calculated a Living Standards Index to characterize
204 socioeconomic status using principal components analysis based on household assets and
205 dwelling characteristics, as previously described (39). To compare baseline infant diet, in the egg
206 arm, we only included subjects for whom the 6-month interview was completed before
207 intervention delivery began and applied the age distribution of these subjects (6.0 ± 0.1 mo) to
208 the control arm by comparing the percentage of subjects falling into subgroups (i.e., 5.9, 6.0, and

209 6.1 months). Differences in baseline characteristics were assessed using generalized estimating
210 equations (GEE) with an exchangeable correlation structure to adjust for clustering in linear and
211 logistic regression models. For categorical variables, multinomial regression models were
212 specified with robust standard error estimation to account for clustering. To assess intervention
213 compliance, we estimated the proportion of infants for whom caregivers reported to have
214 consumed any eggs provided by the trial in the past 24 hours at 9 and 12 months, and the
215 proportion of trial egg consumed (whole egg, greater than half, half, or less than half).

216 We calculated LAZ, WLZ, and WAZ at 6 and 12 months according to the WHO
217 Multicentre Growth Reference Study growth standards (2). Infants with measurements outside
218 biologically plausible ranges ($|z\text{-score}| > 6$ for LAZ, $|z\text{-score}| > 5$ for WLZ, and $z\text{-score} > 5$ or $< -$
219 6 for WAZ) were excluded from analyses (2, 40). Prevalence of stunting, wasting, and
220 underweight were calculated based on the proportion of infants with LAZ < -2 , WLZ < -2 , WAZ
221 < -2 , respectively. To compare the mean response in continuous outcomes of length, weight,
222 LAZ, WLZ, and WAZ at 12 months between the egg and control groups, linear regression
223 models were developed with GEE to account for within-cluster correlation. For dichotomous
224 outcomes of stunting, wasting and underweight at 12 months, log-binomial regression models
225 with GEE were used to account for clustering and to estimate prevalence ratios. Robust Poisson
226 regression with GEE was used for dichotomous outcomes when models failed to converge (41,
227 42). Each model included a variable indicating treatment allocation (egg intervention versus
228 control) and was adjusted for the baseline measure of the outcome variable. To test for
229 interaction between the egg and enteric pathogen control interventions, we added a variable for
230 allocation to the antibiotic intervention or placebo and an interaction term in each model. *P*-
231 values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

232 Missing data were handled in the following ways. Losses to follow-up were examined to
233 determine if they were balanced across arms. Baseline characteristics of infants lost to follow up
234 or who had missing data on length or weight at 6 or 12 months were compared with those who
235 had complete data. The reasons for missingness on the outcome variables and covariates were
236 explored. All analyses were performed using Stata version 14.2 (StataCorp LP, College Station,
237 TX).

238

239 **Results**

240 In total, 3398 infants from 283 clusters were eligible for enrollment in the egg or control
241 arms of the trial (**Figure 1**). Parental consent was obtained for 3051 infants (89.8%) from 283
242 clusters when they reached 3 months of age. Following consent, anthropometric data at 12
243 months were available for 2601 infants (85.3%); 12-month anthropometric data were missing for
244 <1% of subjects due to the switch to telephone visits in April 2020. Among those with available
245 outcome data, baseline anthropometric data were missing for ~10% of infants. After excluding
246 subjects missing baseline measurements, 1228 infants in the egg arm from 142 clusters and 1109
247 infants in the control arm from 141 clusters were included in analyses. Missing data on baseline
248 and outcome measures were primarily due to not meeting subjects before they aged out of
249 eligibility for the respective interview. The percentage of subjects without completed 12-month
250 interviews was highest in August 2019. No differences in the number of met versus not met
251 cases were observed by cluster. Overall, loss to follow-up by 12 months was 13.5% and did not
252 differ by treatment arm; no clusters were lost. The baseline characteristics of those included in
253 analyses and those with missing data differed by maternal age and education, paternal
254 occupation, household size, and report of infant having a cough, cold or difficulty breathing in

255 the past seven days; however, differences were of small magnitude (**Supplemental Table 1**).

256 Baseline infant anthropometry was comparable between those with complete and missing data.

257 Household and parental baseline characteristics were balanced between trial arms (**Table**
258 **1**). Infant baseline characteristics were also balanced between arms (**Table 2**). Across arms, the
259 majority of infants had mothers with primary education (70.6%) and fathers who worked as day
260 or contract laborers (33.9%) or owned their own business (34.2%). Most lived in households
261 with improved toilets (60.7%). At baseline, infants were a mean age of 6.3 ± 0.3 months across
262 arms. Mean length and weight were 64.6 ± 2.5 cm and 6.9 ± 0.9 kg, respectively. Mean LAZ,
263 WLZ, and WAZ were -1.1 ± 1.0 , -0.4 ± 1.1 , and -1.1 ± 1.0 , respectively. Prevalence of stunting,
264 wasting, and underweight was 18.5%, 6.0%, and 16.4%, respectively. Breastfeeding was almost
265 universal (98.3%) The most common morbidity reported in the past week was cough, cold, or
266 difficulty breathing (52.5%), followed by fever (13.8%), diarrhea (2.4%), and dysentery (1.0%).

267 Most infants in the egg arm (83.6%) began receiving the intervention prior to the 6-
268 month interview. In the baseline dietary comparison, intake of complementary foods did not
269 differ between groups (**Table 2**). Subjects included in the baseline dietary analysis were younger
270 and had lower intake of complementary foods than those excluded (**Supplemental Table 2**).
271 There were no significant differences in anthropometric outcomes between infants who began
272 the intervention prior to the baseline interview and those who began after the interview
273 (**Supplemental Table 3**). Almost all (~98%) of subjects in each arm received nutrition
274 education.

275 Intervention compliance was high with almost all subjects in the egg arm consuming trial
276 eggs at 9 and 12 months (**Table 3**). In both arms, mean LAZ, WLZ, and WAZ was lower at 12
277 months than at the 6-month timepoint (**Table 4**). The prevalence of stunting, wasting, and

278 underweight was higher at 12 months of age compared to 6 months (**Table 5**). There was no
279 statistically significant difference in mean LAZ ($\beta = 0.05$, 95% CI: -0.01, 0.10) or prevalence of
280 stunting (PR = 0.98, 95% CI: 0.89, 1.13) between the egg and control arms at 12 months,
281 adjusting for baseline measures of the outcomes. Infants in the egg arm had significantly higher
282 mean weight ($\beta = 0.07$ kg, 95% CI: 0.02, 0.11) and WAZ ($\beta = 0.06$, 95% CI: 0.02, 0.11) relative
283 to the control at 12 months. We found no significant interaction between the egg and enteric
284 pathogen control interventions on LAZ (p-value = 0.271) or any of the secondary outcomes in
285 adjusted analyses. The consumption of other ASF (fish, dairy, liver, flesh meat) did not differ
286 between arms (**Supplemental Table 4**). Fish was the most commonly consumed ASF, other than
287 the eggs provided by the trial. In the control group, ~40% of infants consumed eggs at 12 months
288 in the past 24 hours.

289

290 **Discussion**

291 In a cluster-randomized controlled trial in rural Bangladesh, the provision of a daily egg
292 for 6 months during the early complementary feeding period did not have a significant effect on
293 linear growth from 6 to 12 months of age. Although the adjusted mean difference in LAZ
294 between arms at 12 months suggested a trend toward improved length in the egg arm, this
295 difference was not statistically significant. However, the egg intervention had a significantly
296 positive impact on ponderal growth. The results from this trial add to the literature on the effect
297 of ASF consumption on early growth and suggest that regular consumption of eggs, although
298 beneficial for weight gain, is not necessarily sufficient to reduce the decline in linear growth.
299 These findings emphasize the complexity of factors that contribute to linear growth faltering and

300 demonstrate how a potentially scalable food-based intervention may influence early growth in a
301 rural South Asian setting.

302 Our findings that the egg intervention did not have a significant benefit on LAZ or
303 stunting prevalence are similar to those of the egg trials in rural Malawi and South Africa but
304 differ from the trial in Ecuador, which found a significant treatment effect on linear growth (19,
305 20). This variation in findings may be attributable to differences in nutritional status, which may
306 have influenced subjects' response to eggs as an intervention. The burden of undernutrition was
307 highest in the Ecuador study population, where mean LAZ at baseline was -1.9 and stunting
308 prevalence was 38%. Baseline anthropometry was more comparable between our study
309 population (LAZ = -1.1; stunting prevalence: 18.5%) and that of Malawi (LAZ = -0.9; stunting
310 prevalence: 14%) and South Africa (stunting prevalence: 23.8%).

311 There were similarities and differences in infant diet across study populations. Typical
312 staple foods in Ecuador and Bangladesh included rice and potato, versus maize in Malawi. In
313 terms of ASF, fish was most commonly consumed in Malawi and Bangladesh, versus eggs and
314 meat in Ecuador, and milk in South Africa. In our study area, infants' intakes of numerous
315 micronutrients, including B-vitamins, vitamins D and E, calcium, iron, and zinc, have been
316 found to be inadequate relative to recommendations (43). A secondary analysis from our study
317 found that mean usual intakes for energy, protein, and most micronutrients were higher in the
318 egg arm compared to the control at 9 and 12 months, but the proportion of infants meeting
319 recommendations for most micronutrients remained <50% among those receiving the
320 intervention (44). It is possible that we did not find a treatment effect because the micronutrients
321 provided by the trial eggs did not sufficiently fill intake gaps.

322 Other contextual factors that affect infant health and nutritional status in Bangladesh may
323 provide further explanation. A high burden of diarrhea is associated with a higher risk of stunting
324 during the first 2 years of life (45). Diarrhea incidence is seasonal in Bangladesh, peaking in the
325 monsoon season (June – September) (46, 47). Seasonal variation in exposure to diarrheal
326 pathogens over the duration of the intervention may have been an influential factor in the growth
327 pathway. However, we did not find that the magnitude of the effect size of the egg intervention
328 on linear growth differed by receipt of treatment for enteric pathogens. In a study in Ecuador
329 following children who had been enrolled in the original egg trial, the effect of the intervention
330 was no longer present in those who had reached 2 to 3 years of age, potentially because of
331 morbidity and other environmental factors that inhibited growth once the trial had ended (48).
332 This finding reinforces the need for long-term, comprehensive strategies to improve growth.

333 It is possible that we did not find a significant effect on linear growth due to the duration
334 of the intervention period. In our study, mean LAZ decreased and the prevalence of stunting
335 increased from 6 to 12 months of age, which follows patterns of growth faltering found in the
336 region and was expected in this setting, where infants and children are often exposed to
337 numerous factors (e.g., low birthweight, poor diet quality, high disease exposure) that place them
338 at higher risk; previous trials have observed comparable trends (30, 49). As growth faltering
339 typically continues past 12 months of age, it is uncertain if intervening solely from 6 to 12
340 months was sufficient to observe an effect (50). Furthermore, linear growth is characterized by a
341 pattern of saltation and stasis, with increases in length occurring in episodic incremental bursts
342 that interrupt periods with no measurable growth (51). Among infants experiencing growth
343 faltering, these bursts may be reset by the complex network of physiological and environmental
344 factors influencing the growth process (52). This may further explain why we did not observe a

345 treatment effect by the 12-month visit as the unpredictable timing of growth bursts in this setting
346 may not have been captured within the timeframe of our study. Additionally, ponderal and linear
347 growth do not necessarily occur concurrently; increases in weight may precede increases in
348 length (53-55). A study analyzing growth across populations in the United States, Ghana, and
349 Honduras found that WLZ and weight change in infancy within a 3-month period were
350 correlated with increased length gain in the following 3-month period, demonstrating a need to
351 continuously monitor growth over time. Intervention periods longer than 6 months may therefore
352 be necessary to adequately assess the effect of regular intake of eggs and other ASF on linear
353 growth. Observation on how subjects in our study continued to grow after 12 months of age is
354 necessary.

355 The increase in weight and WAZ that we observed among subjects receiving a daily egg
356 is consistent with results from a meta-analysis of trials testing ASF supplementation, finding
357 supplementation significantly increased weight ($N = 23$ estimates; WMD: 0.09 kg; 95% CI:
358 0.06, 0.13) and WAZ ($N = 15$; WMD = 0.05; 95% CI: 0.00, 0.10) among term infants and
359 children (14). The most common ASF in these trials was milk; our trial contributes knowledge
360 on the impact of an egg intervention to this body of evidence, (19). The effect we found on
361 ponderal growth possibly occurred because the trial eggs reduced an energy gap (44). Eggs have
362 greater energy and nutrient density than rice, the typical staple food in Bangladesh (56). Studies
363 have shown that increasing energy density may be beneficial for growth when typical
364 complementary foods are low in energy density and infants are unable to consume greater
365 amounts of these foods or be fed more frequently, assuming there is also an increase in total
366 energy intake (57)..

367 In the context of the nutrition transition and growing double burden of malnutrition,
368 which Bangladesh is experiencing, it is important to contextualize our findings on weight as
369 weight gain in early life may be a risk factor for overweight, obesity, and non-communicable
370 diseases (NCD) in adulthood (58, 59). Gaining weight faster than expected relative to linear
371 growth may contribute to an increased risk of NCDs, particularly if this occurs after the age of 2
372 years (60). In our study, the higher mean weight in the egg arm versus control, while significant
373 and consistent with other ASF trials among infants and children, was not of a magnitude
374 indicative of a rapid increase in weight relative to length, particularly as we also observed a
375 positive trend in linear growth among subjects receiving the intervention.

376 There were some limitations in our study. Consumption of trial eggs was reported
377 through a questionnaire and not directly observed. It is possible that households in the egg group
378 sold or gifted the eggs provided or that there was contamination across study arms. However,
379 given that the study area was large and cluster lines had been clearly delineated, it is unlikely that
380 subjects in different arms communicated or shared trial eggs. Compliance with the intervention
381 was also monitored weekly, allowing field staff to provide support to caregivers facing feeding
382 challenges. The trial was partially blinded, which could have resulted in biased outcome
383 assessments. However, interviewers were standardized and highly trained, and had experience
384 objectively assessing anthropometry in previous trials. Nutrition education was provided to all
385 arms and included messaging on ASF, which may have influenced caregivers' feeding practices
386 in the control arm that could have attenuated the impact of the intervention; any potential
387 behavior change associated with the messaging was not within the constraints of the study to
388 assess. There was also a relatively high number of subjects with incomplete 6- and 12-month
389 interviews, resulting in missingness in the data. It is possible that the holidays and harvest

390 seasons that occurred during the data collection period affected the ability of interviewers to
391 reach subjects. Despite these challenges, the study team made repeated attempts to reach
392 subjects. Additionally, despite missingness, the study retained a large sample size.

393 In this rural setting in Bangladesh, the provision of a daily egg for 6 months to infants
394 starting at ~6 months of age did not significantly reduce the decline in linear growth, indicating
395 that daily egg intake would not be sufficient to slow linear growth faltering where various
396 factors, such as the typical diet, hygiene and sanitation, and disease exposure, contribute to
397 growth faltering. Our finding that the egg intervention significantly slowed the decline in
398 ponderal growth demonstrates the benefit of including eggs early in the diet. As this is the first
399 trial to our knowledge to assess the effect of providing a daily egg on growth in rural South Asia,
400 our findings contribute to the evidence base on the role ASF consumption plays in early growth
401 and development across geographic regions. Additional research is necessary to assess the effect
402 of a full year of the intervention, as the critical time to intervene on growth extends beyond 12
403 months of age.

404

405 **Acknowledgments**

406 The authors would like to express their gratitude to Laura Caulfield, Jessica Fanzo, and
407 John McGready at the Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, and to the study
408 participants. The authors' responsibilities were as follows – MIH, KJS, MA, KPW, TA, ABL,
409 and ACP designed the research; MMP, SS, MTI, HA, RH, KA, BD, KH, KA, and F-TJ
410 conducted the research; MMP and LS-FW analyzed the data; MMP wrote the manuscript; MMP
411 and ACP had primary responsibility for final content. All authors read and approved the final
412 manuscript.

413 Data described in the manuscript, code book, and analytic code will be made available upon
414 request pending application and approval.

References

1. Dewey KG, Mayers DR. Early child growth: how do nutrition and infection interact? *Matern Child Nutr* 2011;7 Suppl 3:129-42.
2. WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group. WHO child growth standards based on length/height, weight and age. *Acta Paediatr Suppl* 2006;450:76-85.
3. Victora CG, Adair L, Fall C, Hallal PC, Martorell R, Richter L, Sachdev HS. Maternal and child undernutrition: consequences for adult health and human capital. *Lancet* 2008;371(9609):340-57.
4. National Institute of Population Research and Training (NIPORT) and ICF. Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey 2017-18. Dhaka, Bangladesh and Rockville, Maryland, USA: NIPORT and ICF, 2020.
5. Campbell RK, Hurley KM, Shamim AA, Shaikh S, Chowdhury ZT, Mehra S, de Pee S, Ahmed T, West KP, Jr., Christian P. Effect of complementary food supplementation on breastfeeding and home diet in rural Bangladeshi children. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2016;104(5):1450-8.
6. Rah JH, Akhter N, Semba RD, de Pee S, Bloem MW, Campbell AA, Moench-Pfanner R, Sun K, Badham J, Kraemer K. Low dietary diversity is a predictor of child stunting in rural Bangladesh. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 2010;64(12):1393-8.
7. Neumann C, Harris DM, Rogers LM. Contribution of animal source foods in improving diet quality and function in children in the developing world. *Nutr Res* 2001;22:193-220.
8. Dagnelie PC, van Dusseldorp M, van Staveren WA, Hautvast JG. Effects of macrobiotic diets on linear growth in infants and children until 10 years of age. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 1994;48 Suppl 1:S103-11; discussion S11-2.
9. Ruel MT. Milk intake is associated with better growth in Latin America: evidence from the Demographic and Health Surveys. *FASEB J* 2012;17:A1199.
10. Allen LH. The nutrition CRSP: what is marginal malnutrition, and does it affect human function? *Nutr Rev* 1993;51(9):255-67.

11. Marquis GS, Habicht JP, Lanata CF, Black RE, Rasmussen KM. Breast milk or animal-product foods improve linear growth of Peruvian toddlers consuming marginal diets. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1997;66(5):1102-9.
12. Kaimila Y, Divala O, Agapova SE, Stephenson KB, Thakwalakwa C, Trehan I, Manary MJ, Maleta KM. Consumption of animal-source protein is associated with improved height-for-age z-scores in rural Malawian children aged 12-36 months. *Nutrients* 2019;11(2).
13. Shapiro MJ, Downs SM, Swartz HJ, Parker M, Quelhas D, Kreis K, Kraemer K, West KP, Fanzo J. A systematic review investigating the relation between animal-source food consumption and stunting in children aged 6-60 months in low and middle-income countries. *Adv Nutr* 2019;10(5):827-47.
14. Pimpin L, Kranz S, Liu E, Shulkin M, Karageorgou D, Miller V, Fawzi W, Duggan C, Webb P, Mozaffarian D. Effects of animal protein supplementation of mothers, preterm infants, and term infants on growth outcomes in childhood: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2019;110(2):410-29.
15. Grillenberger M, Neumann CG, Murphy SP, Bwibo NO, Weiss RE, Jiang L, Hautvast JG, West CE. Intake of micronutrients high in animal-source foods is associated with better growth in rural Kenyan school children. *Br J Nutr* 2006;95(2):379-90.
16. Long JK, Murphy SP, Weiss RE, Nyerere S, Bwibo NO, Neumann CG. Meat and milk intakes and toddler growth: a comparison feeding intervention of animal-source foods in rural Kenya. *Public Health Nutr* 2012;15(6):1100-7.
17. Krebs NF, Mazariegos M, Chomba E, Sami N, Pasha O, Tshetu A, Carlo WA, Goldenberg RL, Bose CL, Wright LL, et al. Randomized controlled trial of meat compared with multimicronutrient-fortified cereal in infants and toddlers with high stunting rates in diverse settings. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2012;96(4):840-7.
18. Tang M, Sheng X-Y, Krebs NF, Hambidge KM. Meat as complementary food for older breastfed infants and toddlers: a randomized, controlled trial in rural China. *Food Nutr Bull* 2014;35(Suppl 3):S188-S92.
19. Iannotti LL, Lutter CK, Stewart CP, Gallegos Riofrio CA, Malo C, Reinhart G, Palacios A, Karp C, Chapnick M, Cox K, et al. Eggs in early complementary feeding and child growth: a randomized controlled trial. *Pediatrics* 2017;140(1).

20. Stewart CP, Caswell B, Iannotti L, Lutter C, Arnold CD, Chipatala R, Prado EL, Maleta K. The effect of eggs on early child growth in rural Malawi: the Mazira Project randomized controlled trial. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2019.
21. Ricci H, Faber M, Ricci C, Kruger HS, Malan L, Nakiranda R, Visser M, Smuts CM. Effects of egg as an early complementary food on growth of 6- to 9-month-old infants: a randomised controlled trial. *Public Health Nutr* 2023;27(1):e1.
22. Iannotti LL, Lutter CK, Bunn DA, Stewart CP. Eggs: the uncracked potential for improving maternal and young child nutrition among the world's poor. *Nutr Rev* 2014;72(6):355-68.
23. Semba RD, Shardell M, Sakr Ashour FA, Moaddel R, Trehan I, Maleta KM, Ordiz MI, Kraemer K, Khadeer MA, Ferrucci L, et al. Child stunting is associated with low circulating essential amino acids. *EBioMedicine* 2016;6:246-52.
24. Dewey KG. The challenge of meeting nutrient needs of infants and young children during the period of complementary feeding: an evolutionary perspective. *J Nutr* 2013;143(12):2050-4.
25. Iannotti LL, Lutter CK, Waters WF, Gallegos Riofrio CA, Malo C, Reinhart G, Palacios A, Karp C, Chapnick M, Cox K, et al. Eggs early in complementary feeding increase choline pathway biomarkers and DHA: a randomized controlled trial in Ecuador. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2017;106(6):1482-9.
26. Semba RD, Zhang P, Gonzalez-Freire M, Moaddel R, Trehan I, Maleta KM, Ordiz MI, Ferrucci L, Manary MJ. The association of serum choline with linear growth failure in young children from rural Malawi. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2016;104(1):191-7.
27. Millward DJ. Nutrition, infection and stunting: the roles of deficiencies of individual nutrients and foods, and of inflammation, as determinants of reduced linear growth of children. *Nutrition Research Reviews* 2017;30(1):50-72.
28. Thorne-Lyman AL, Valpiani N, Akter R, Baten MA, Genschick S, Karim M, Thilsted SH. Fish and meat are often withheld from the diets of infants 6 to 12 months in fish-farming households in rural Bangladesh. *Food Nutr Bull* 2017;38(3):354-68.
29. Labrique AB, Christian P, Klemm RD, Rashid M, Shamim AA, Massie A, Schulze K, Hackman A, West KP, Jr. A cluster-randomized, placebo-controlled, maternal vitamin A

- or beta-carotene supplementation trial in Bangladesh: design and methods. *Trials* 2011;12:102.
30. Christian P, Shaikh S, Shamim AA, Mehra S, Wu L, Mitra M, Ali H, Merrill RD, Choudhury N, Parveen M, et al. Effect of fortified complementary food supplementation on child growth in rural Bangladesh: a cluster-randomized trial. *Int J Epidemiol* 2015;44(6):1862-76.
 31. West KP, Jr., Shamim AA, Mehra S, Labrique AB, Ali H, Shaikh S, Klemm RD, Wu LS, Mitra M, Haque R, et al. Effect of maternal multiple micronutrient vs iron-folic acid supplementation on infant mortality and adverse birth outcomes in rural Bangladesh: the JiVitA-3 randomized trial. *Jama* 2014;312(24):2649-58.
 32. West KP, Jr., Christian P, Labrique AB, Rashid M, Shamim AA, Klemm RD, Massie AB, Mehra S, Schulze KJ, Ali H, et al. Effects of vitamin A or beta carotene supplementation on pregnancy-related mortality and infant mortality in rural Bangladesh: a cluster randomized trial. *Jama* 2011;305(19):1986-95.
 33. Rah JH, Christian P, Shamim AA, Arju UT, Labrique AB, Rashid M. Predictors of stunting and thinness in post-menarcheal adolescent girls in rural Bangladesh. *Public Health Nutr* 2009;12(12):2400-9.
 34. Merrill RD, Shamim AA, Ali H, Jahan N, Labrique AB, Schulze K, Christian P, West KP, Jr. Iron status of women is associated with the iron concentration of potable groundwater in rural Bangladesh. *J Nutr* 2011;141(5):944-9.
 35. European Commission. Agriculture and rural development: Eggs. Internet: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/animal-products/eggs_en (accessed September 4, 2022).
 36. Alive and Thrive. Internet: www.aliveandthrive.org (accessed August 9, 2020).
 37. Menon P, Nguyen PH, Saha KK, Khaled A, Sanghvi T, Baker J, Afsana K, Haque R, Frongillo EA, Ruel MT, et al. Combining intensive counseling by frontline workers with a nationwide mass media campaign has large differential impacts on complementary feeding practices but not on child growth: results of a cluster-randomized program evaluation in Bangladesh. *J Nutr* 2016;146(10):2075-84.

38. Chowdhury ZT, Hurley KM, Campbell RK, Shaikh S, Shamim AA, Mehra S, Christian P. Novel method for estimating nutrient intakes using a semistructured 24-hour diet recall for infants and young children in rural Bangladesh. *Curr Dev Nutr* 2020;4(9):nzaa123.
39. Gunnsteinsson S, Labrique AB, West KP, Jr., Christian P, Mehra S, Shamim AA, Rashid M, Katz J, Klemm RD. Constructing indices of rural living standards in Northwestern Bangladesh. *J Health Popul Nutr* 2010;28(5):509-19.
40. de Onis M, Garza C, Victora CG, Onyango AW, Frongillo EA, Martines J. The WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study: planning, study design, and methodology. *Food Nutr Bull* 2004;25(1 Suppl):S15-26.
41. Petersen MR, Deddens JA. A comparison of two methods for estimating prevalence ratios. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 2008;8:9.
42. Chen W, Qian L, Shi J, Franklin M. Comparing performance between log-binomial and robust Poisson regression models for estimating risk ratios under model misspecification. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 2018;18(1):63.
43. Campbell RK, Hurley KM, Shamim AA, Shaikh S, Chowdhury ZT, Mehra S, Wu L, Christian P. Complementary food supplements affect dietary nutrient adequacy and home food consumption in children 6-18 mo old in a randomized controlled trial in rural Bangladesh. *J Nutr* 2018;148:1-8.
44. Pasqualino MM, Shaikh S, McGready J, Islam MT, Ali H, Ahmed T, West KP, Jr., Alam M, Hossain MI, Labrique AB, et al. An Egg Intervention Improves Dietary Intakes but Does Not Fill Intake Gaps for Multiple Micronutrients among Infants in Rural Bangladesh. *J Nutr* 2023;153(4):1199-210.
45. Checkley W, Buckley G, Gilman RH, Assis AM, Guerrant RL, Morris SS, Mølbak K, Valentiner-Branth P, Lanata CF, Black RE, et al. Multi-country analysis of the effects of diarrhoea on childhood stunting. *Int J Epidemiol* 2008;37(4):816-30.
46. Das SK, Begum D, Ahmed S, Ferdous F, Farzana FD, Chisti MJ, Latham JR, Talukder KA, Rahman MM, Begum YA, et al. Geographical diversity in seasonality of major diarrhoeal pathogens in Bangladesh observed between 2010 and 2012. *Epidemiol Infect* 2014;142(12):2530-41.
47. Platts-Mills JA, Babji S, Bodhidatta L, Gratz J, Haque R, Havt A, McCormick BJ, McGrath M, Olortegui MP, Samie A, et al. Pathogen-specific burdens of community

- diarrhoea in developing countries: a multisite birth cohort study (MAL-ED). *Lancet Glob Health* 2015;3(9):e564-75.
48. Iannotti LL, Chapnick M, Nicholas J, Gallegos-Riofrio CA, Moreno P, Douglas K, Habif D, Cui Y, Stewart C, Lutter CK, et al. Egg intervention effect on linear growth no longer present after two years. *Matern Child Nutr* 2020;16(2):e12925.
 49. Christian P, Kim J, Mehra S, Shaikh S, Ali H, Shamim AA, Wu L, Klemm R, Labrique AB, West KP, Jr. Effects of prenatal multiple micronutrient supplementation on growth and cognition through 2 y of age in rural Bangladesh: the JiVitA-3 Trial. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2016;104(4):1175-82.
 50. Victora CG, de Onis M, Hallal PC, Blossner M, Shrimpton R. Worldwide timing of growth faltering: revisiting implications for interventions. *Pediatrics* 2010;125(3):e473-80.
 51. Lampl M, Veldhuis JD, Johnson ML. Saltation and stasis: a model of human growth. *Science* 1992;258(5083):801-3.
 52. Lampl M. Saltation and stasis. In: Cameron N, Bogin B, eds. *Human growth and development*. 2nd ed. Cambridge, MA: Academic Press, 2012.
 53. Costello AM. Growth velocity and stunting in rural Nepal. *Arch Dis Child* 1989;64(10):1478-82.
 54. Waterlow JC. Relationship of gain in height to gain in weight. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 1994;48 Suppl 1:S72-3; discussion S3-4.
 55. Brown KH, Black RE, Becker S. Seasonal changes in nutritional status and the prevalence of malnutrition in a longitudinal study of young children in rural Bangladesh. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1982;36(2):303-13.
 56. Institute of Nutrition and Food Science. *Food Composition Table for Bangladesh*. Dhaka, Bangladesh: University of Dhaka, 2013.
 57. Dewey KG, Adu-Afarwuah S. Systematic review of the efficacy and effectiveness of complementary feeding interventions in developing countries. *Matern Child Nutr* 2008;4 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):24-85.

58. Adair LS, Fall CH, Osmond C, Stein AD, Martorell R, Ramirez-Zea M, Sachdev HS, Dahly DL, Bas I, Norris SA, et al. Associations of linear growth and relative weight gain during early life with adult health and human capital in countries of low and middle income: findings from five birth cohort studies. *Lancet* 2013;382(9891):525-34.
59. Biswas RK, Rahman N, Khanam R, Baqui AH, Ahmed S. Double burden of underweight and overweight among women of reproductive age in Bangladesh. *Public Health Nutr* 2019;22(17):3163-74.
60. Victora CG, Rivera JA. Optimal child growth and the double burden of malnutrition: research and programmatic implications. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2014;100(6):1611s-2s.

Figure 1. Participant flow diagram of a six-month protein intervention comparing the effect of the provision of a daily egg versus control on growth.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of households and parents of infants enrolled into a six-month intervention trial comparing the effect of the provision of a daily egg versus control on growth, by intervention group¹

Characteristic	Control (N = 1511)		Egg (N = 1540)	
	<i>n</i>	% or Mean ± SD	<i>n</i>	% or Mean ± SD
Household				
Household size	1492	4.5 ± 2.1	1526	4.5 ± 1.9
LSI quintile				
1st (lowest)	1492	20.6	1526	19.3
2nd		19.2		19.4
3rd		20.4		20.7
4th		20.0		19.4
5th (highest)		19.8		21.2
Religion				
Muslim	1492	92.2	1526	91.9
Hindu		7.8		8.1
None		0.0		0.1
Latrine				
None/field/bush	1492	3.3	1526	4.3
Open latrine		21.7		18.8
Improved latrine		59.6		61.8
Flush toilet		15.4		15.1
Parental				
Maternal age, y	1467	23.5 ± 5.4	1480	23.5 ± 5.6
Maternal education				
No schooling	1490	9.7	1521	11.3
Class 1 to 9		71.3		70.0
SSC passed		5.6		6.4
11 years and above		13.4		12.3
Paternal occupation				
Farmer/sharecropper	1309	12.1	1326	12.7
Laborer		35.3		32.6
Business owner		33.2		35.3
Private service		16.8		16.7
Other		2.7		2.8

LSI, Living Standards Index calculated based on household assets and dwelling characteristics using principal components analysis.

SSC, Secondary School Certificate.

¹Linear or logistic regression models with generalized estimating equations or multinomial regression models with robust variance estimation were used to compare characteristics between groups. There were no differences between groups.

Table 2. Baseline characteristics of infants enrolled into a six-month intervention trial comparing the effect of the provision of a daily egg versus control on growth, by intervention group¹

Characteristic	Control (N = 1511)		Egg (N = 1540)	
	<i>n</i>	% or Mean ± SD	<i>n</i>	% or Mean ± SD
Age, mo	1297	6.3 ± 0.3	1426	6.3 ± 0.3
Sex, M	1511	52.0	1540	51.2
Anthropometry				
Birthweight, kg ²	508	2.65 ± 0.42	450	2.66 ± 0.42
Length, cm	1278	64.59 ± 2.50	1407	64.57 ± 2.44
Weight, kg	1278	6.87 ± 0.90	1412	6.87 ± 0.87
LAZ	1278	-1.14 ± 1.06	1407	-1.11 ± 1.04
WLZ	1268	-0.39 ± 1.10	1401	-0.39 ± 1.05
WAZ	1278	-1.07 ± 1.07	1412	-1.04 ± 1.01
Stunting, LAZ <-2	1278	19.2	1407	17.7
Wasting, WLZ <-2	1268	5.6	1401	6.4
Underweight, WAZ <-2	1278	17.8	1412	15.2
Breastfed	1297	98.1	1425	98.5
24 hr intake, any ³				
Cereals/tubers	254	44.1	202	47.6
Legumes		5.4		4.3
Dairy		15.8		13.8
Fish		9.9		7.1
Flesh meat		0.5		1.2
Liver		6.4		4.7
Eggs		13.4		11.8
Vitamin A-rich F/V		3.5		4.3
Vitamin C-rich F/V		2.5		2.8
Snacks		38.6		33.9
Morbidity, last 7 days				
Cough/cold/difficulty breathing	1297	51.9	1425	53.1
Diarrhea	1296	2.5	1425	2.3
Dysentery	1293	0.6	1420	1.3
High fever	1293	14.2	1421	13.4

LAZ, length-for-age z-score; WLZ, weight-for-length z-score; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score.
F/V, fruit and vegetables

¹Linear or logistic regression models with generalized estimating equations or multinomial regression models with robust variance estimation were used to compare characteristics between groups. There were no differences between groups.

²Data on birthweight were collected among infants measured 0-72 hours after birth.

³To compare diet, the egg arm was restricted to subjects for whom the six-month interview was completed before the first visit from the field distributor. The age distribution of these subjects was then applied to the control arm.

Table 3. Compliance with the intervention at follow-up visits among infants in a six-month intervention trial comparing the effect of the provision of a daily egg versus control on growth, egg arm¹

	9 mo (<i>n</i> = 1142)	12 mo (<i>n</i> = 712)
Egg consumption	%	%
Any intake, last 24 hr	97.0	99.3
Provided by trial, any intake in last 24 hr	96.4	99.0
Amount consumed		
Whole egg	89.3	96.5
More than half	2.8	1.4
Half	3.8	0.8
Less than half	0.5	0.3
None	3.6	1.0
Provided by household, any	13.5	22.1

¹Nine-month estimates include subjects with complete total egg intake at 9-months. Twelve-month estimates include subjects who were still receiving the intervention at the time of the 12-month interview.

Table 4. Effect of the provision of a daily egg on attained length, weight, LAZ, WLZ, and WAZ after the six-month intervention

Characteristic	12 months		Unadjusted Mean Difference ¹		Adjusted Mean Difference ²	
	Control (<i>n</i> = 1109)	Egg (<i>n</i> = 1228)	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i> - <i>value</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i> - <i>value</i>
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD				
Length, cm	71.18 \pm 2.59	71.33 \pm 2.61	0.15 (-0.08 , 0.38)	0.21	0.14 (0.00 , 0.28)	0.06
Weight, kg	8.07 \pm 1.00	8.13 \pm 0.99	0.07 (-0.02 , 0.15)	0.15	0.07 (0.02 , 0.11)	0.003
LAZ	-1.53 \pm 1.00	-1.46 \pm 1.01	0.07 (-0.02 , 0.16)	0.14	0.05 (-0.01 , 0.10)	0.09
WLZ	-0.75 \pm 1.02	-0.69 \pm 1.00	0.06 (-0.03 , 0.15)	0.21	0.06 (0.00 , 0.13)	0.065
WAZ	-1.32 \pm 1.02	-1.24 \pm 1.00	0.08 (-0.01 , 0.17)	0.08	0.06 (0.02 , 0.11)	0.005

LAZ, length-for-age z-score; WLZ, weight-for-length z-score; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score.

¹Linear regression with generalized estimating equations.

²Linear regression with generalized estimating equations, adjusted for the baseline value of the outcome.

Table 5. Effect of the provision of a daily egg on prevalence of stunting, wasting, and underweight after the six-month intervention

Characteristic	12 months		Unadjusted ¹		Adjusted ²	
	Control (<i>n</i> = 1109) %	Egg (<i>n</i> = 1228) %	PR (95% CI)	<i>P</i> - <i>value</i>	PR (95% CI)	<i>P</i> - <i>value</i>
Stunting, LAZ <-2	30.4	27.8	0.91 (0.79 , 1.05)	0.19	0.98 (0.89 , 1.13)	0.69
Wasting, WLZ <-2	10.7	9.3	0.87 (0.66 , 1.15)	0.32	0.91 (0.78 , 1.29)	0.44
Underweight, WAZ <-2	24.1	21.3	0.88 (0.74 , 1.04)	0.14	0.90 (0.85 , 1.18)	0.19

LAZ, length-for-age z-score; WLZ, weight-for-length z-score; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score.

¹Log-binomial regression with generalized estimating equations.

²Robust Poisson regression with generalized estimating equations, adjusted for the baseline value of outcome.